

Monitoring of dangerous environmental factors engineering

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Abstract: *Criteria for the selection of tools for rating information obtained. A systematic approach and modern hardware from the mathematics of scientific studies, expert valuation was carried out using the method, and methods to the synthesis of existing scientific theories on this issue, this gave him an opportunity.*

Keywords: *Work, production, engineering, protection, human organizimi, toxic substances, safety, labor.*

Of the republic of Uzbekistan in the organization to ensure healthy and safe working conditions, prevention of accidents in production, and with them the problem of reducing the economic losses associated with the production of associated diseases remains very topical.

The life and health of employees of the republic of Uzbekistan for the protection of the constitution, the labor code, "on labour protection", the "Radianttsiyaviy on security is"on, "on industrial safety of hazardous production facilities"on, "on technical regulation", "on social protection of disabled people in the republic of Uzbekistan from the'-on"rising, "on compulsory insurance of civil liability of the employer is"on, "on conformity assessment" and the laws of the republic of Uzbekistan, documents, sanitary rules and norms, normative and legal acts on labor protection issues in the field of technical regulation and other documents with guaranteed [1].

Of the relevance of the topic. Also on the costs of the manufactured product engineering in the economy of uzbekistan, which stands on the number of employees in the first place. In the year 2021, according to official data of uzbekistan, production of sanitary norms and hygiene in the field of working conditions which do not respond to nearly 20 percent work in [2]. Machine-building enterprises in the workplace by employers, labor conditions in the state of unsatisfactory preparation and implementation stages of work is the result of not paying enough attention to the issues of labor protection.

Results. Instrumental for the implementation of control and monitoring in the workplace involving accredited laboratories in the prescribed manner. Our own production of production control in the work place (the plant) in our laboratory can perform their scope of accreditation can be monitored and the standardized physical-chemical factors include the necessary measuring equipment. A special assessment of labor conditions, according to the state of uzbekistan ministry of labor and the employer included in the register by third party organisations that are involved in providing services in the field of labor protection is carried out together. Testing laboratory accredited by the national accreditation body should be the organization's participants.

Trade unions and the labour inspectors, trade union organizations and trade unions, which works on behalf of the committee on labor protection authorized (authorized) by the control function in accordance with labour legislation and other individuals, employers of labour law compliance has the right to the containing document.

As a result of the unhappy things in this production;

35 condition of tools, equipment and the effects of various solids;

Be the shock position 16 units;

29 may fall in case;

34 units in position to fall from a height;

46 in case of a traffic accident;

15 burn in case;

16 the descent of the units in a different position on things

1 case to sink in;

Injury by other person in position 3;

Classification of air pollutants in the workplace, the conditional analysis method are shown as follows. 3-the table

N/a 0	Index	analysis methods		
		for chemical	, physical-chemical	Physical
1	the lowest level of MPC, mg / l	and 0.1 - 1	0,005 - up to 0.05	0,001-0,01
2	of the detection accuracy %	0,01-0,5	1-10	2-20
3	Selective	good	high	very high
4	the duration of the analysis (samples prepared), min	30-200	15-60	10-30
5	Mass in the ability to perform rapid analysis	of low	average	high
6	the ability to automate	low	average	high
7	to measure the cost of the equipment, which is rel. units	1	20-100	100-500

Among the above methods in control of the production of harmful substances, pollutants, the components of the environment which is the most commonly used analysis the analysis of physical-chemical (instrumental) the high sensitivity of the method, the accuracy of the analysis results to be repeated in an optimal way and combines the qualities of the like.

Production control production control measured during the directory list approved by the head of production of the enterprise is carried out in accordance with the control program. Most importantly the production of certain types of labor in the work place-specific and defining the conditions factors and indicators.

The implementation of production control in the work place of the enterprise in the workplace refers to all factors that are available higienik the full measure of the level of exposure and allows you to get objective information. At the same time, the company's own laboratory accreditation and laboratory studies and tests involved in the procedure established by the laboratory is carried out independently by [3;4;5;6].

The condition of the work place from the point of view of the assessment for the implementation of the norms higienik complex monitoring and control system is applied to the valuation of labor in the special conditions [13]. Special conditions of work consistently performed this assessment of complex events.

Thus, the valuation of labor conditions in the work place labor organization using a special mechanism that allows the lens to evaluate the conditions of this highlight problematic areas in the field of production and labor conditions on the improvement of measures you need to work out.

The analysis shows that the parameters of harmful production factors and research methods of measurement of the measuring equipment performed using physical-chemical methods of analysis of the control and monitoring is the most often used.

Boholash production control and special conditions of working, the methods and the accuracy of the results of the analysis of these methods with a high sensitivity of the qualities, like repeated combines in an optimal way.

Machine-building enterprises in the context of control and the improvement of existing and the introduction of a new system manitoringgini to measure refers to the modernization of the complex. The production for use in the evaluation of labor conditions in the context of the most viable measure chemicals in the air of the workplace in relation to the targeted legislative many portable measurement of indicators of the device does not require additional sample preparation they aimed at.

This question of the choice of analysis method did not separate the measuring equipment to the solution of many small shows. During the research, three approaches were considered.

First universal system based on chemical analysis.

The second approach for measuring one parameter that should be chosen taking xisobga indicators remain unlimited determines that equipment. A practical approach analytical tools for laboratory equipment include third kvametriya the basics of rational choice. However, the above-mentioned theories and methods of the object compared to control conditions qo'llaniladigon work in practice is complicated.

The considered approach on the basis of manitoringi bajaridigon instrumental in the completion of work in the field of laboratory testing and control method of the choice of equipment are offered.

The equipment, methods of functional, technical, ekspluatsion, ergonomic and cost indicators, which include legislative boholash muofiq to the list of criteria is based on expert valuation method.

Conclusion. Machine-building enterprises on the basis of the analysis of the main technological processes of showing the negative effects on the health of workers will determine the factors of production. Key measures for the improvement of labor conditions in the engineering industry are considered in the work place, and one of them of dangerous and harmful production factors, the improvement of monitoring and control system. System engineering and enterprise of its lower - monitoring and control of dangerous and harmful production factors in the workplace of the system is caused by the usual system of labor protection of the analysis. Tools for the control of dangerous and harmful production factors in the workplace and the control methodology in the selection of measurement tools with the selection of the basis of existing theoretical approaches are considered.

The chemical substances are different from each other;

- on the nature of the effect on the human body: toxic, irritation, allowing the sensibilizatsiya kanserogen, mutagen, into influencing the reproductive function;
- with the method of entry into the human body: the respiratory system, the gastrointestinal tract, through the skin and mucous membranes;

In such a situation the quality of the individual ingredients only designed for specific and quantitative analysis of the chemical analysis of multidisciplinary methods and tools for effective because they narrow the results tanlanmagan reason does not provide the required quality or is not economically feasible. The method and device is required because of a wide range sufficiently and as a result, the costs will increase dramatically. Many of the substances monitored in samples with the same attitude that allows more targeted komponentli reliable analytical methods and detection systems in the first place.

To determine the concentration of aerosol in the air of working zone of harmful chemicals and the following apply.

- Take samples to the laboratory-based methods and their chemical analysis in the laboratory research; performed using portable measuring instruments, allowing you to express directly operated facilities in the analysis method.

Moving on the selection of the proposed methodology on the basis of instrumental equipment, control-measuring a functional scheme of the complex has been developed and was based on the theoretical aspects, in particular, the working area of physical-chemical factors of the measurement and standardization of devices is recommended.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Kuchkarova C. H. et al. The High Water Plants Water Road in cleaning //Annual Research & Review in Biology. – 2019. – C. 1-5.
2. Habibullaevna K. C., Xodjakulov M. N. Emergency Situations that May Occur as a Result of Public Disorder, Damage Reduction and Fire Safety Measures //International Journal of Formal Education. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 74-77.
3. Habibullaevna K. C. Fuel Based on Food and Agricultural Organic Waste Development of Safe Technology of Briquettes //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 36-39.
4. Kuchkarova C. H. NATURAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE ALGAE PLANT OF THE TREATMENT OF TELEAROSOVODIS, SYSTEMATIC PLACE AND SEPARATE BIOLOGICAL FEATURES //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – T. 4. – №. 2. – C. 117-124.
5. Habibullaevna K. C., Mohinur N. MONITORING THE IMPACT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE ENVIRONMENT //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 285-288.
6. Habibullaevna K. C., Maftunakhan O. DEVELOPMENT OF SAFE TECHNOLOGY OF FUEL BRIQUETTES //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 281-284.
7. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2023). Protection of Workers Sleep on Modern Solutions. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 43, 225-230.
8. Kh, K. C. (2023). Principles of Development of Engineering Ecology. *American Journal of Engineering, Mechanics and Architecture* (2993-2637), 1(10), 39-41.
9. Кучкарова, Ч. Х. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ОХРАНЫ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАН. *Mexatronika va robototexnika: muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari*, 1(1), 85-87.
10. Kuchkarova, C., Jumanova, M., Tursunov, X., Urinova, S., & Nurmatov, J. (2023, June). Prospects for improving the technology of biological treatment of domestic and municipal waste water. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

11. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2023). Analysis of Industrial and Environmental Safety Management Systems. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(6), 211-214.
12. Kochkarova, C., Abdurakhmanov, A., Jumanova, M., Tursunov, H., & Jalilov, A. (2023). Analysis of urban communal water supply. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 402, p. 09024). EDP Sciences.
13. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2022). MEASURES TO ENSURE NOISE AND VIBRATION SAFETY IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 289-293).